

FNS – Cloud

Food Nutrition Security

Food Nutrition Security Cloud

Deliverable 2.2

Catalogues for Data Sources and Services

Due Date:	30.09.2020
Submission Date:	30.09.2020
Revision Date:	20.09.2021
Dissemination Level:	Public (PU)
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Project acronym: FNS-Cloud

Project Number: 863059

Start date of project: 01.10.2019 **Project duration:** October 2019 – September 2023

Food Nutrition Security Cloud (FNS-Cloud) has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme (H2020-EU.3.2.2.3. – A sustainable and competitive agri-food industry) under Grant Agreement No. 863059 – www.fns-cloud.eu

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D2.2 Catalogues for Data Sources and Services

Document Control Information			
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Dissemination Level	<input type="checkbox"/> CO Confidential <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PU Public		
Approved by	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> RTDS (COO) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> QIB (SCO) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> JSI <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> UCD <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PMT <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> JDLC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> EuroFIR <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> UWTSO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DTU <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ENEA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> HYVE <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> HYLO	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> UM <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NUTRIS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> RIVM <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> WUR <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> UGent <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> IMDEA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> HUA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TUM <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> GS1 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SF <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> UoR <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> IFA	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ILSI <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> BfR <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> AUTH <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> FEM <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> CNR <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> APRE <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> CAP <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> UNIFI <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> LIFE <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Nutritics <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> EFF
Relevant IPRs	Not applicable		
Underlying Datasets	Data collected in partner surveys		

Version/Date	Change/Comment
0.1_2020-06-09	<i>Document and outline creation</i>
0.2_2020-07-28	<i>V1 ready for sharing with the GA</i>
0.3_2020-09-24	<i>V2 ready for SCO and COO review</i>
1.0_2020-09-30	<i>SCO and COO edits integrated, 1.0 submitted to EC</i>
2.0_2021-08-13	<i>Updated deliverable as per experts request for revision</i>
2.1_2021-09-20	<i>SCO inputs integrated</i>

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1 Publishable Summary

The FAIR principles define that data should be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable in order to make it open and useful for the scientific community and to accelerate research and innovation. As datasets are fragmented and distributed all over Europe and beyond, a central index is needed where available datasets are registered. Such a central catalogue should list all available datasets in one place and enable the first FAIR aspect, which is findability. A central catalogue would not contain datasets, but rather information about the author, the purpose and content of the datasets.

Such a central catalogue has already been implemented for the FNS-Cloud as an MVP (minimal viable product) and the implementation consists of a website and a catalogue application. The website is a pilot version of the thematic EOSC cloud FNS-Cloud which later will form the landing page of FNS-Cloud and contain general information about the cloud, the community, and the final catalogue application.

The web application is a catalogue tool where resources such as datasets, tools and services are listed and can be searched. The catalogue application differentiates three types of resources: datasets, tools, and services. Datasets are typically collections of data records while tools are software applications to perform operations on data. A service is considered as a useful labour that somebody can offer like, for instance, collecting data or scientific advice as well as work done by an algorithm via an API. These three types of resources have different properties and therefore different metadata is needed. Such metadata can be name, contact person, target audience, access and usage restrictions, and technical readiness level. A resource can also have a hyperlink to directly access a website containing more detailed information. The catalogue application has a search functionality which not only allows to search terms but also to search in FNS-Cloud research areas and target audience groups. The research areas were taken from D2.1 FNS-Cloud Data Map and correspond to the demonstrator areas of FNS-Cloud. Target audiences were defined by owners of datasets, tools, and service providers.

The process to include a resource into the catalogues, will be defined later in the project and is part of the management process. For this implementation, a simple approach was assumed where a user can register a new resource with an online form. After submitting the form, data will be stored but not published in the catalogues. For this, an administrator user must login into the administrator area and verify the resource after which the resource will be published in the catalogue area.

An additional implemented feature is quality assurance. The goal was to provide information about the quality of a dataset, tool, or service. As no one can know all these resources and automatic evaluation of such diverse resources is difficult, a crowdsourcing approach was chosen. Each user of the catalogue application can rate a resource with up to 5 stars. For each of the resources the average rating and the number of ratings is presented. Finally, the catalogues were filled with data from project partners. Beneficiaries were asked to share information their datasets, tools, and services in two surveys and results were imported into the catalogue databases.

2 Introduction

The FNS (Food Nutrition Security) Cloud is a multifaceted system consisting of several integrated websites, specifically the WP7 Community of Practice (www.myfnsccloud.eu), the project website (www.fns-cloud.eu) and social media pages developed, which is maintained by WP6, and the cloud landing page (www.fnscloud.eu, not yet published), which includes dataset repositories (including WP4 outputs) and catalogues developed by WP2 as well as tools and services developed by WP3 and for the WP5 Demonstrators. For the duration of the EU-funded project, and whilst the cloud is being developed, the project website will be the central hub. As the cloud and resources grow, the cloud site will be more prominent and take over entirely as the landing site when funding ends, retaining a static archive site for the project. The diagram visualising the FNS Cloud components can be found on the next page. While the central cloud and catalogues are being developed in WP2, the high-level metadata will be supplemented by topic-specific metadata developed in WP3 (in particular the new nucleotide metadata structure). The WP3 metadata app will be a backend implementation, allowing for automatic tagging of resources and for the human users this information will be also displayed in the WP2 catalogues. Similarly other services (for example food matching, nutrient estimation, etc.) still under development in WP3 will be added to the services catalogues and accessible directly via APIs.

Deliverable 2.2 Catalogues for data sources and services focuses on catalogues for datasets, tools and services linked to FNS Cloud, existing and emerging, and search functionalities.

Catalogues are one of the main features of a European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) described in the Implementation Roadmap for EOSC, in particular connections to datasets and services¹. One of the main EOSC goals is to create a virtual environment that will federate available datasets, services, and tools to enable data-driven science and accelerate innovation². Many research projects around Europe, including those funded by the EU, generate large volumes of data as well as tools to analyse data, but awareness about these resources is fragmented, access is not equitable, and researchers lack both skills and confidence to exploit them fully.

¹ http://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/pdf/swd_2018_83_f1_staff_working_paper_en.pdf

² <https://www.eosc-portal.eu/about/eosc>

D2.2 Catalogues for Data Sources and Services

Figure 1 Cloud architecture.

2.1 Requirements for catalogues

Design and implementation of catalogues for initiatives like FNS-Cloud contribute to the FAIR principles³ which defines data to be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable. A catalogue tool contributes to that principle, by making datasets Findable for humans. A catalogue should be implemented as web application and should map readily to EOSC.

FNS-Cloud catalogues must improve the findability of resources by storing information about them in a common database. The information about resources should be standardised, enabling it to be found whether searching FNS-Cloud, EOSC or another search engine. Enabling findability by computers is another contribution of a catalogue app to the FAIR principle.

³ Wilkinson, Mark D.; Dumontier, Michel; Aalbersberg, IJsbrand Jan; Appleton, Gabrielle; et al. (15 March 2016). "The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship". Scientific Data. 3: 160018. doi:10.1038/sdata.2016.18

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Further, FNS-Cloud catalogues must improve accessibility by providing contact information to owners (persons or organisations) to gain access in the event the resources are not open access.

Finally, the FNS-Cloud catalogue GUI (graphical user interface) needs to be clear and user-friendly, facilitating the finding of and access to resources. Interoperability and reusability of resources are out of scope for a catalogue tool and will be supported through standards and APIs (Application Programming Interfaces) and licensing models (e.g., Open Source) as well as different spoken languages, as provided by the tools or services and datasets. The catalogues will store information about the interoperability and re-usability of the resources, encouraging providers to take these aspects into account when developing their tools, datasets or services.

2.2 Existing catalogues

FNS-Cloud serves as part of a broader part of the EOSC landscape, is a thematic EOSC cloud and several similar projects have run or are running simultaneously (e.g., Blue-Cloud) at different stages of development. In order to learn from their experience and utilise best practices, an analysis of other EOSC-related websites was performed. In addition, some European research infrastructures in the domain of Health and Food such as Elixir and BBMRI-ERIC were identified, and their catalogue tools were investigated. Finally, some projects and consortia in the direction of eScience such as OpenAIRE were investigated. Below are some examples of catalogues implemented by EOSC projects and research infrastructures (although the EOSC Marketplace might not be considered a catalogue and more a portal that is a sort of meta-meta level, that should in turn contain information about the FNS Cloud, but not all the details about its resources, like the FNS Cloud catalogue does). A full list can be found on the EOSC Portal site⁴ as well as a list of established research infrastructures on the European Commission website⁵.

⁴ <https://www.eosc-portal.eu/about/eosc-projects>

⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/strategy/european-research-infrastructures/eric/eric-landscape_en

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Figure 2 EOOSC Catalogue and Marketplace - <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/>

Figure 3 BBMRI-ERIC Directory - <https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/menu/main/app-molgenis-app-biobank-explorer/biobankexplorer>

Figure 4 Open AIRE Catalogue - <http://catalogue.openaire.eu/search>

Figure 5 OpenRiskNet Services <https://openrisknet.org/e-infrastructure/services/>

2.3 Creating an inventory of resources

2.3.1 Tools and services

To collect information for FNS Cloud, a survey was conducted, designed and evaluated by Task 2.2 contributors, and sent to all Beneficiaries, asking about tools and services they use or develop during FNS-Cloud as well as those they know about that might be useful in the context of food nutrition security. The survey asked the following questions:

2.3.1.1 Tools

Table 1 Tools survey questions.

Contact	FNS-Cloud Partner
	Contact person
	E-mail
General information	Name of the tool
	Tool description
	Who is the owner of the tool?
	Is the tool pre-existing or do you plan to implement it in the FNS-Cloud project?
	For how long has the tool been operational?
	For what type of food data or food-related data is the tool? e.g., food composition, food consumption, food waste, contamination, microbiome, DNA etc.
	In what language is the tool?
	Does the tool support multilingual? (Y/N)
	Link to the tool and/or its documentation
Who is the target audience?	

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	Are there access or usage restrictions?
	Is the tool open source?
	What is the licensing model? (Is there a cost for the license? Is it free to use? Are there some maintenance and support fees?)
	Is it a web app, a desktop app, or a mobile app?
Technical information	EU Technology Readiness Level (TRL) (https://bit.ly/2P6DyG2 , 1-9)
	Is there a possibility to self-host the tool or to install the tool on own machines? (Y/N)
	What technologies were used to develop the tool? (i.e., Python, JavaScript, PHP)
	What data import interfaces and formats are available? (i.e., EXCEL file import or API with SSD2 JSON format etc.)
	What data export interfaces and formats are available? (i.e., EXCEL file import or API with SSD2 JSON format etc.)
Collaboration options in international, national, or private projects	Is non-profit collaboration possible? (Y/N)
	Is joint-project collaboration possible? (Y/N)
	Is commercial collaboration possible? (Y/N)
	Any other information?

2.3.1.2 Services
Table 2 Services survey questions.

Contact	FNS-Cloud Partner
	Contact person
	E-mail
General information	Name of the service
	Service description
	For what type of food data or food-related data is the service? e.g., food composition, food consumption, food waste, contamination, microbiome, DNA etc.
	Who offers the service?
	Is the service pre-existing or do you plan to prepare or implement it in the FNS-Cloud project?
	How many times has the service been performed?
	Is the service language or country specific?
	Link to service
	Who is the target audience?
	Are there access or usage restrictions?
	Is the service free of charge or does it cost? And does it differ for commercial, non-profit, research, governmental or private users?
Technical information	EU Technology Readiness Level (TRL) (https://bit.ly/2P6DyG2 , 1-9)
	Is non-profit collaboration possible? (Y/N)

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Collaboration options in international, national, or private projects	Is joint-project collaboration possible? (Y/N)	
	Is commercial collaboration possible? (Y/N)	
	Any (what languages are used, how long does it take to perform, etc.)	other information

The surveys collected information about 7 services and 39 tools.

2.3.2 Datasets

To populate the FNS Cloud dataset catalogues, and define metadata necessary to describe datasets, the survey conducted by WP4 and WP5 was used where more than 60 datasets were identified, including information such as ownership, limitations, and technical details (e.g., size, export formats, ontologies used). However, the emphasis in this project will be on newly collected datasets in WP4.

2.3.3 Resource meta-data

Based on the collected information, a set of meta-data attributes were selected and are described in the following sub-sections. This model has been implemented in the MVP version of the catalogues, with the possibility of further extension in the final version.

2.3.3.1 Tools and services

Table 3 Selected meta-data for describing tools and services.

Attribute	Description	Field type
Name	Name of the tool or service	Text field; Mandatory
Description	Description of the tool or service	Long text field
Provider	Provider of the tool or service	Text field; Mandatory
Type	Tool or service	Radio button; Mandatory
Status	If the tool or service is integrated into FNS Cloud or is being integrated	Radio button; Mandatory
Technology Readiness Level	Estimated maturity of the tool or service	Scale 1-9 or N/A; Mandatory
Has API	If the tool uses a (standard) API	Boolean
Is Open Source	If the tool is Open Source	Boolean
URL	Link to find more details about the tool or service	Text field
Contact - Person	Name and surname of the contact person responsible for the tool or service	Text field; Mandatory
Contact - Email	Email address of the contact person	Text field; Mandatory
Target audience	Target audience description	Long text field

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Access and usage restrictions	Access and usage restrictions description	Long text field
Supported languages	Languages supported by the tool or during service provision	Text field
Technical details – Open Source	Details about the Open Source license	Long text field
Technical details – Implementation	Details about the implementation: mobile, web or desktop app, algorithm, etc.	Long text field
Technical details – Tech stack	Technology stack used for implementation (for example Java, Node.js, PostgreSQL)	Long text field
Technical details – Import capabilities	How data can be imported into the tool (for example EXCEL, API, CSV)	Long text field
Technical details – Export capabilities	How data can be exported from the tool (for example PDF, API, CSV)	Long text field
Collaboration possibilities:	If collaboration is possible in case of non-profit/joint-project/commercial initiatives	Boolean
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Non-profit ● Joint-project ● Commercial 		
Other information	Other information the tool/service owner would like to provide	Long text field
Tags – Food Map areas	Classification to areas from the Food Map	Multiselect
Tags – Target Audience(s)	Classification to pre-defined target audiences	Multiselect

2.3.3.2 Datasets
Table 4 Selected meta-data for describing datasets.

Attribute	Description	Field type
Name	Name of the dataset	Text field; Mandatory
Description	Description of the dataset	Long text field
Provider	Provider of the dataset	Text field; Mandatory
Has API	Is the dataset available via a (standard) API	
URL	Link to find more details about the dataset	Text field
Contact - Person	Name and surname of the contact person responsible for the tool or service	Text field; Mandatory
Contact - Email	Email address of the contact person	Text field; Mandatory
Target audience	Target audience description	Long text field

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Access and usage restrictions	Access and usage restrictions description	Long text field
Supported languages	Languages in which is the dataset	Text field
Quality process	Description of the quality process of the dataset	Long text field
Size	Size of the dataset	Long text field
Export capabilities	In what formats the dataset can be exported (for example PDF, API, CSV)	Long text field
Collaboration possibilities:	If collaboration is possible in case of non-profit/joint-project/commercial initiatives	Boolean
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Non-profit ● Joint-project ● Commercial 		
Other information	Other information the dataset owner would like to provide	Long text field
Tags – Food Map areas	Classification to areas from the Food Map	Multiselect

3 Design and implementation

Development of the FNS Cloud catalogue tool and the landing page (www.fnscloud.eu, not yet published) was performed in two steps: design and technical implementation.

3.1 Design

A set of design inspirations was selected from the research described above (Section 2.1) and a low-fidelity design prepared using Adobe XD, which focused mostly on the layout and information architecture.

Figure 6 Low-fidelity landing page designs and inspirations from other EOOSC websites.

The next step was preparation of a high-fidelity design with branding provided by WP6. Images used were obtained from royalty-free stocks and edited as necessary using Adobe Photoshop; icons were obtained from <https://fontawesome.com/> and additional graphics were drawn using Inkscape.

Figure 7 FNS-Cloud logo and fonts and colour schemes used for the design.

The high-fidelity design was prepared in two layouts – widescreen (for monitors and laptops) and mobile (for smartphones), to guide the responsive implementation of the website.

3.2 Technical implementation

Since one of the aims of FAIR is accessibility, FNS Cloud was developed as a web-based application, allowing access from a range of devices. The system consists of two elements:

- Informational portal
- Catalogue application

The primary functional requirement for the informational portal was management of content by users that do not have IT experience (project administrators). Because of this requirement, the portal was implemented using the WordPress content management system. Additionally, the following reasons supported the choice of WordPress:

- Most used CMS on top 1 million and top 10 million websites⁶
- Open-source and free to use
- Has a large set of standard features that are useful for website management, including:
 - Extended page content editor
 - Capacity to add information at certain time (delayed posting)
 - Management of media files (pictures, videos, documents)
 - Extensibility with plugins

For performance reasons, however, the number of plugins utilised in the front-end have been limited and created bespoke from scratch.

The catalogue application, on the other hand, had different functional requirements:

⁶ <https://trends.builtwith.com/cms> and https://w3techs.com/technologies/overview/content_management

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1. **Submit** a resource⁷ to the application and have it reviewed by administrator before showing it on the page
2. **Search** the resources by title/author and/or specified meta-attributes (such as food-areas or target audiences)
3. **Rate** the resources inside application, possibly limited only to users of FNS-Cloud in the future

For this, WordPress was also selected, because it allowed a working prototype to be created quickly, facilitating user testing and feedback gathering from the Beneficiaries.

3.3 Usability testing

Although usability testing was not planned, the catalogue app is a major feature of a EOSC cloud or a research infrastructure and it was therefore decided to conduct usability testing later in the project. To ensure the FNS Cloud is fit-for-purpose and high-quality, usability testing will be performed in cooperation with WP6 in several rounds. Two approaches are planned for each round:

- a) Supervised usability testing during a teleconference
- b) Unsupervised usability testing with a survey to complete, providing feedback

Early testing will be conducted with users selected from Beneficiaries.

Supervised usability testing – focussing on navigation – is planned for up to five participants, who will be subject to a one-to-one call with a researcher from WP2 and WP6 experienced in such guided learning. Usability test scenarios prepared in collaboration with WP6 will guide the (test) subject through processes designed to reveal how future users might engage with the catalogues and highlight any issues with navigation. The calls will be recorded for later analysis.

The same usability testing scenario will be sent to 25 other test participants who will complete the processes independently and provide feedback in the form of a systems usability scale (SUS) questionnaire, developed originally by John Brooke at Digital Equipment Corporation⁸.

Table 5 System Usability Scale.

System Usability Scale	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
I think that I would like to use this system frequently.					
I found the system unnecessarily complex.					

⁷ tool, service, or dataset

⁸ Brooke, J. (1986). "SUS: a "quick and dirty" usability scale". In P. W. Jordan; B. Thomas; B. A. Weerdmeester; A. L. McClelland (eds.). Usability Evaluation in Industry. London: Taylor and Francis.

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I thought the system was easy to use.					
I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system.					
I found the various functions in this system were well integrated.					
I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system.					
I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly.					
I found the system very cumbersome to use.					
I felt very confident using the system.					
I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system.					

Results from both test types will be analysed and included in D6.8 as well as informing further development of the FNS Cloud catalogues and cloud as a whole.

4 User Manual

Users can be categorised as external (not logged in) or Admin users. During the run of the FNS-Cloud project, the WP2 leader will appoint a person for the Admin role and after this project is finished, the appointment of the Admin user will be done by the institution or community ruling the project at that time.

In the future, a different role is planned, for a logged in user, who will take over some of the regular user permissions and have additional access to FNS Cloud resources. This will be implemented in Task 2.4 Implement authentication and authorisation infrastructure.

4.1 External User

An external user is anyone who opens the catalogues. They do not need to have an account or log in order to use the tool.

4.1.1 Searching for resources

Tools and services are listed in a separate catalogue from datasets, so users need to decide first what resource they are looking for, i.e., dataset or tools and services.

Figure 8 Catalogues home page with access points to the Datasets and Tools & Services search engines marked.

The search engines have similar layouts, in that they both have a free text search field, where users can enter a phrase and/or details against which resources will be scanned. Matching results will be sorted by relevance, that is how the search term matches the resource name and description. The search results are currently ordered by:

- whether the entire sentence is matched
- if all the search terms are within the titles
- if any of the search terms appear in the titles
- if the full sentence appears in the contents⁹

Other search and sorting functionalities will be added in the future, based on user feedback. In both search engines, it is possible to search by food area(s), which are derived from tags in the FNS-Cloud Food Map (see D2.1 for further details).

⁹ https://developer.wordpress.org/reference/classes/wp_query/#order-orderby-parameters

Figure 9 Tools & services catalogue search.

Figure 10 Datasets catalogue with an example search.

Tools and Services search functionality also allows searching by target audience (e.g., Business & Developers, General Public, Researchers & Scientists) and results can be filtered to show only tools, only services, or both. Users can select a resource from the results and preview details

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 863059.

about resources and rate them on a scale from 1-5. In the future, this functionality will be restricted to logged in users only.

Home > Datasets

Example dataset
Example Co.
★★★★★ 4.5 (2)

Classification & Description

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consetetur sadipscing elitr, sed diam nonumy eirmod tempor invidunt ut labore et dolore magna aliquyam erat, sed diam voluptua. At vero eos et accusam et justo duo dolores et ea rebum. Stet clita kasd gubergren, no sea takimata sanctus est Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consetetur sadipscing

CONTACT:

Person: John Doe
Email: john@doe.com

DETAILS:

Target audience: Example target audience.
Access and usage restrictions: Example access and usage restrictions.
Supported languages: English
Quality process: Example quality process.

TECHNICAL DETAILS:

Export capabilities: Example export capabilities.
Data size: Example size.

COLLABORATION POSSIBILITIES:

Non-profit: Yes
Joint-project: Yes
Commercial: Yes

OTHER INFORMATION:
Example other information.

Rate this dataset
Click on a star to rate it!

★★★★★
Average rating 4.5 / 5. Vote count: 2
Thank you for rating this post!

API <https://platform.test.fns.foodcase-services.com/>

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Figure 11 Example dataset details.

4.1.2 Adding resources

Regular users can also add resources to the catalogue. To do this, they need to access the submission form for either datasets or tools and services and complete at least the mandatory information (as stated in Table 3 and Table 4), which relates to metadata descriptions. After adding a resource, it will be approved by an Admin user prior to publication.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 863059.

Home > Datasets > Add New Dataset

ADD NEW DATASET

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consetetur sadipscing elitr, sed diam nonumy eirmod tempor invidunt ut labore et dolore magna aliquyam erat, sed diam voluptua. At vero eos et accusam et justo duo dolores et ea rebum. Stet clita kasd gubergren, no sea takimata sanctus est Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consetetur sadipscing.

Title *

Content

Visual | Text

Paragraph **B** *I*

Owner *

Has API

 No

Url

ADD NEW DATASET

Figure 12 Dataset submission form.

The detailed approach for the onboarding process of resources is a management concern and will be decided in other WPs. As the onboarding process is not decided yet, this simple approach with registration and verification was implemented for the moment.

4.2 Admin User

Admin users have an account and extended permissions related to the site (4.2.1) and resources (4.2.2).

4.2.1 CMS (Content Management System)

Admin users can access and change functionalities (media, pages, plugins, users, tools, and settings) from the main menu in the Admin panel¹⁰ or plugins.

Figure 13 FNS Cloud Admin Panel in WordPress.

4.2.2 Resource validation

In addition, there are two entries in the main menu related to FNS Cloud catalogues:

- Tools & Services
- Datasets

There Admin users can find a list with all submitted resources with those that need to be approved for publication marked as pending.

¹⁰ <https://wordpress.org/support/>

Figure 14 Table of datasets, with an Example dataset pending approval.

Admin users can also review resources' metadata and edit them, as necessary. If any crucial information is missing or seems incorrect they should contact the person responsible for the resource to clarify. They can also preview the resource, to see how it will look on the website, before publication and publish the resource in the catalogues.

Figure 15 Example dataset details before approval.

Figure 16 Resource submission, approval, and publication process.

5 Lessons Learned

During implementation and discussion with project partners, some issues were detected, and new ideas were discussed which will be listed here as lessons learnt.

- The implementation of the catalogue app as WordPress plugin was good for rapid prototyping but caused problems when requirements started to increase. For a later implementation, an own implemented web application should be preferred as the flexibility is maximised and the integration with EOSC and other clouds and research infrastructure can be tailored.
- Rating of the resources is an example of the restriction given by WordPress. The plugin only allowed public rating and it was not possible that only registered users can rate a resource. For future, only registered and logged in users should be able to rate a resource and should be able to post a comment for their rating. Additionally, a multi-dimensional rating can be implemented, with specific criteria that should be rated upon, where not only the content of the dataset can be rated but also aspects like amount of content, feasibility for certain use cases and so on. The idea is to have a more detailed quality and usability rating scheme which is innovative and not seen in the investigated catalogue apps. Datasets from different FNS-Cloud might have different quality criteria. For example, for food composition data EuroFIR has developed a detailed quality evaluation questionnaire, while for other areas such information might not yet exist. In the scope of FNS-Cloud, quality criteria are being developed in WP4 for intake/consumption data.
- As search results can be quite extensive, an idea came up to have a sorting and filtering of search results by relevance, date, alphabet, or user rating. Currently the results are only sorted by relevance.
- Currently, the admin user in WordPress can verify newly registered resources. For the future it would be helpful if another role is defined for this task as the administrator is a global role and not designed for content and intrinsic tasks.
- In the submission form for new resources, GDPR and Terms of Services should be added to inform users how the data will be used.
- Only logged in users can submit and update their resources.
- Connection to data repositories (FairSpace, Zenodo, etc.).
- Integration with the Metadata app and other services developed in WP3.
- Integration with the FNS Cloud AAI.
- Adding the functionality for the catalogue to be machine-searchable, by making the APIs public.
- Connection to API documentation in Swagger.
- The catalogue is compliant and in-line with other catalogue tools in EOSC and research infrastructures. EOSC started to implement the EOSC marketplace where scientific data sources are listed. As the number of thematic clouds in EOSC is lower than 10, the marketplace is feasible. But as soon as more research areas will contribute, it will be hard to have a central catalogue app which is able to provide all specialities of the different research areas. This means that the different research catalogues like ours must be connected to the EOSC. The question of how is still open.

